

PROTECTIVE PROPERTIES OF NITROGEN AND BORON-CONTAINING INHIBITORS FOR OIL AND GAS PIPELINES

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Abstract. Several technical innovations have been created to solve the current challenges of protecting pipelines from corrosion and external influences in oil and gas production processes, greatly increasing production. This process has a negative impact on production and requires the use of a corrosion inhibitor.

Keywords: corrosion inhibitor, boron, nitrogen, metals, oleic acid, test, speed, level of protection.

Introduction. This test is used to study the properties of oil-soluble corrosion inhibitors containing nitrogen and boron. Corrosion inhibitors consist of one or more functional groups, which are organic substances containing hydrocarbon atoms in their molecules. The main functional groups are nitrogen, oxygen and boron groups.

An analysis of foreign experience in the production of oil-soluble corrosion inhibitors shows that synthetic fatty acids are used as raw materials for the creation of corrosion inhibitors, and the production of fatty acids is increasing year by year. The fact that oil-soluble corrosion inhibitors containing nitrogen and boron are double-bonded chemical compounds has a significant impact on their high protective efficacy, as the molecules adsorbed by the inhibitors, which have double bonds in hydrocarbon radicals, react with the metal to form cross-links.

Materials and methods. Corrosion inhibitors play an important role in protecting metals from corrosion. The research processes were tested according to the standard methods of GOST 9.506-87. They comply with the GOST 9.506-87 standard for corrosion inhibitors. The corrosion protection ability of inhibitors used in water and oil environments to protect structural materials of communications and equipment made of metal alloys in the oil and gas industries from corrosion can be determined by the gravimetric method.

The gravimetric method allows you to determine the mass loss of metals. In this case, the level of protection of the inhibitor is determined by the change in the corrosion rate of the samples in an environment without an inhibitor and in an environment with an inhibitor at different times. At least three metal samples are taken in each experimental test and the experiments are tested.

Result and discussion. The use of corrosion inhibitors is one of the most important and common methods of protecting metals from corrosion in various industries. With the emergence of new technologies in metallurgy, oil and gas wells, petrochemicals and oil refining, the scope and variety of inhibitors is constantly expanding, therefore, research on methods of influencing corrosion, establishing the properties of inhibitors, clarifying the selection of materials, studying methods of internal coating and application of corrosion inhibitors does not lose its relevance and is an important scientific and technical task. To date, several thousand effective inhibitors and inhibitor compositions have been studied to solve the problems of equipment protection, corrosion processes and influencing factors such as CO₂ and H₂S in various industries. The lack of effective multifunctional protective agents that distinguish them remains a problem. One of the most serious threats to the integrity of any oil and gas well (based on ISO 16530 [1, 2] standards) is corrosion,

which can lead to production shutdowns, explosions, and high-risk incidents. Our DOB-1 brand corrosion inhibitor, which we synthesized as a result of our research, is widely used in protecting oil and gas wells from corrosion. The IR spectrum of this DOB-1 brand corrosion inhibitor was obtained and analyzed.

Figure 1. IR spectrum of DOB-1 corrosion inhibitor

The composition and structure of the DOB-1 corrosion inhibitor were studied using IR-spectrometer technology (IR-Fure, SHIMADZU, Japan) in the range up to 4000 cm^{-1} . The absorption line of the IR spectroscopy of the DOB-1 brand corrosion inhibitor used for protection is analyzed in detail in the following IR spectrum, especially the regions that confirm the presence of boron and nitrogen: 3008.95 cm^{-1} : This signal indicates aromatic C–H stretching vibrations. This range indicates the presence of aromatic chains. 2922.16 and 2850.79 cm^{-1} : This range corresponds to the stretching vibrations of the CH_2 and CH_3 groups. This indicates aliphatic chains, which indicate the presence of hydrocarbon bonds. 2378.23 and 2308.19 cm^{-1} : This region is dominated by $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ or $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching vibrations, which may indicate the presence of nitrogen. This signal can be particularly strong if a $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ bond is present. 1622.13 cm^{-1} : This range typically corresponds to stretching vibrations of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ (amine) bonds or aromatic $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bonds. This is an important signal indicating nitrogen groups and aromatic structure. 1716.65 cm^{-1} : This signal corresponds to the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ (carbonyl) bond. Carbonyl groups are often found in the structure of corrosion inhibitors. 1456.26 and 1409.96 cm^{-1} : These signals represent the deformation vibrations of the CH_2 and CH_3 groups and usually indicate the presence of aliphatic groups. 1273.02 cm^{-1} : This corresponds to the stretching vibration of the C–N bond and may indicate the presence of nitrogen. 1022.27 cm^{-1} : This corresponds to the C–B stretching vibration, indicating the presence of a boron atom. 596.00 cm^{-1} : This signal corresponds to the B–N bond, confirming the presence of a chemical bond between boron and nitrogen.

Metal samples are prepared for the experiment, and in accordance with the requirements of GOST 9.905.82, it is required to use flat-surfaced metals (plates). Sample masses before the experiment:

In solution without inhibitors:

$M_1 = 478.21 \text{ mg} = 0.47821 \text{ g}$

In a medium with 1% DOB-1 inhibitor: $M_2 = 445.11 \text{ mg} = 0.44511 \text{ g}$;

In a medium with 3% DOB-1 inhibitor: $M_3 = 469.72 \text{ mg} = 0.46972 \text{ g}$;

In a medium with 6% DOB-1 inhibitor: $M_4=497.18 \text{ mg}=0.49718 \text{ g}$.

The atmospheric pressure in the testing device was carried out for 120 hours at 3 different concentrations. The test time is calculated from the moment the samples are placed in the environment. The test duration is determined based on GOST 9.905.82. To determine the optimal concentration, we change the concentration of the inhibitor from low to high, and tests are carried out simultaneously. Sample weights after testing: in an environment without inhibitors: $M_1=383.85 \text{ mg}=0.38385 \text{ g}$; in a medium with 1% DOB-1 inhibitor: $M_2=434.92 \text{ mg}=0.43492 \text{ g}$; in a medium with 3% DOB-1 inhibitor: $M_3=465.66 \text{ mg}=0.46566 \text{ g}$; in a medium with 6% DOB-1 inhibitor: $M_4=497.18 \text{ mg}=0.49718 \text{ g}$. In this case, the surface area of the samples= $0.00160\text{--}0.00193 \text{ m}^2$.

Determination of corrosion rates and protection levels of inhibitors

Sample number	Sample surface S, m ²	Sample mass before testing M, g	Sample mass after testing M, g	Sample mass loss, M ₁ -M ₂ , g	V _{n.i} Corrosion rate in an inhibitor-free environment, g/ m ² *s	V _i Corrosion rate in an inhibitory environment, g/ m ² *s	Protection level (Z)%
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Inhibitor-free	0,00160	0,47821	0,38385	0,09436	0,4914	-	-
1%	0,00192	0,44511	0,43492	0,01019	-	0,04411	91,02
3%	0,00193	0,46972	0,46566	0,00406	-	0,01747	96,44
6%	0,00170	0,49718	0,49634	0,00084	-	0,00410	99,16

The corrosion rate and protection level of inhibitors are determined using test results. The protection levels in inhibitory media are 91.02%, 96.44% and 99.16%, respectively, for concentrations of 1%, 3% and 6%.

Conclusion. This IR spectrum contains many important signals confirming the presence of nitrogen and boron. In particular, the signal corresponding to the C–B bond at 1022.27 cm^{-1} and the presence of the B–N bond at 596.00 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of compounds of boron and nitrogen. In addition, bands such as 1622.13 cm^{-1} , 1273.02 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of nitrogen groups, while 1716.65 cm^{-1} probably represents a carbonyl group. Based on this analysis, it is highly likely that the spectrum is consistent with a complex structure containing nitrogen and boron elements along with aliphatic and aromatic groups. According to the results of this analysis, it was determined that the DOB-1 corrosion inhibitor we tested contained nitrogen and sulfur.

Test results of corrosion inhibitors at atmospheric pressure for samples. Experiments were conducted in laboratory equipment in accordance with the requirements of GOST 9.905-82 for 120 hours at 3 different concentrations.

The corrosion rate and protection level of corrosion inhibitors were determined using test experiments. The test results show that the protection levels of DOB-1 brand corrosion inhibitor solutions in oil and gas products at 1%, 3%, and 6% are 91.02%, 96.44%, and 99.16%, respectively. We can use our DOB-1 brand inhibitor, which contains nitrogen and boron in its corrosion inhibitor composition, to protect oil pipelines.

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